

Pharmacist-led intervention reduced drug-related problems in the management of type 2 diabetes mellitus patients

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Abstract

This pre- and post-quasi-experimental study was undertaken to analyze the impact of pharmacist-led intervention (PI) on the reduction of DRPs in the management of type 2 diabetes mellitus outpatients (n = 106) for six months admitted to Prof. Dr. Chairuddin P. Lubis Hospital, Medan, Indonesia. The required data of patients in the control group (CG) and PI groups were extracted from medical records. DRPs were analyzed by applying PCNE version 9.1. The significance of PI on DRPs was analyzed using a paired t-test. The mean age of the patients was 58.61 ± 8.89 (years). Most (54.72%) of them were female. The total incidences of DRPs in CG and PI groups were 263 and 205, respectively, ($p = 0.001$). The relative risk of PI on DRPs was 0.93 and the absolute risk reduction was 6.6%. This study indicated that PI through patient counseling reduced the incidence of DRPs in the management of T2DM outpatients.

Keywords

DRPs, PCNE, Pharmacist-led intervention, T2DM

Introduction

Diabetes mellitus is a serious chronic metabolic disease characterized by hyperglycaemia and multiple complications, such as cardiovascular and chronic kidney disease. The worldwide incidence of DM reached 537 million people in 2021. In Southeast Asia, Indonesia was positioned as the country with the highest prevalence of DM (Sun et al. 2022). To avoid complications, it is crucial to treat T2DM effectively (Jackson 2019).

Medication therapy plays a central role in managing T2DM, but it often involves complex regimens with

multiple drugs, each with its potential side effects. This complexity increases the risk of DRPs (Schroeder 2022). The incidence of DRPs in the management of T2DM patients can be severe, causing an increase in hospital admissions due to poor glycemic control and long-term comorbidities, including cardiovascular disease, neuropathy, and nephropathy. These comorbidities could significantly cause a negative impact on the patient's health, quality of life, and healthcare costs (Hadia et al. 2021).

The pharmacist's expertise in pharmacotherapy and medication management uniquely positions them to play a critical role in preventing and resolving DRPs.

They can provide comprehensive patient education, counselling, and medication reconciliation services to ensure safe and effective medication (Lee et al. 2015). Pharmacist intervention ensures that the medications are appropriately prescribed, significantly improving patient safety and optimizing medication outcomes. Their expertise in pharmacotherapy, patient counselling, and medication reconciliation empowers them to effectively address DRPs and enhance medication adherence (Khartabil et al. 2024). A literature review shows that five studies reported the positive impact of PI on the detection and management of DRPs (Staynova et al. 2024). A study confirmed that T2DM patients need PI through patient education and counselling since most had poor knowledge and attitudes (Banu et al. 2021). Previous studies indicate that PI has various positive impacts on treatment. In addition, it is necessary to highlight that PI promises a significant reduction in DRPs.

Patients who received PI through pharmacist-led education experienced significantly reduced fasting blood glucose levels and improved self-management behaviours, such as medication adherence, dietary control, and physical activity (Lusiana and Wijoyo 2024). Self-management in T2DM involves patients actively engaging in their care through education and self-care behaviours (Fadli et al. 2024). Most PI studies on outpatients with T2DM focus on clinical outcomes and patient quality of life; PI studies related to DRPs are limited. The positive impact of the PI and gaps in previous research led to an analysis of the PI's impact on reducing DRPs in managing T2DM. Therefore, the present study provides insights for health policymakers.

Methods

Selection of participants

This six-month pre- and post-quasi-experimental study compared the DRPs in the management of T2DM outpatients in the CG and PI group admitted to Prof. Dr. Chairuddin P. lubis Hospital, Medan, Province of Sumatera Utara, Indonesia, from February to July 2023. This study included T2DM outpatients older than 18, who had complications, received routine treatment during the study period, were covered by a social health insurance called Badan penyelenggara Jaminan Sosial (BPJS) program, and signed an informed consent after receiving an explanation about this study. The minimum sample size of this study, applying an online sample size calculator, was 98 with 80% power ($1-\beta$ as type II error) and a confidence level ($1-\alpha$) of 95%. The medical record numbers of the study population were randomly selected. The patients whose numbers were selected were then asked about their willingness to participate in this study by signing the informed consent. The number of participants recruited in this study was 106 patients.

Ethical approval

The ethical clearance of this study was issued by The Ethics Committee of Health Research, Universitas Sumatera Utara No. 341/KEPK/USU/2023.

Pharmacist intervention and data collection

The required data for each of the groups, including characteristics of the patients, symptoms experienced by them, the provided drugs, and laboratory results, were recruited from their medical records in the first three months before PI using a self-designed questionnaire. Pharmacist intervention was implemented by distributing brochures on T2DM and providing patient counseling by a pharmacist every month for the patients' visits over the next three months. The brochure contains an explanation of diabetes, its symptoms, how to take and to store the medications appropriately, compliance with the medications, a good diet program for diabetes, and recommended physical activity. Each patient visit/month was followed up by the pharmacist regarding the progress of the disease treatment, medication compliance, and lifestyle improvements. Each patient received an explanation of the study from the pharmacist as a researcher, who also established a schedule for the data collection. The characteristics of the patients were investigated descriptively.

Analysis of drug related problems

The incidence of DRPs in the management of T2DM outpatients was analyzed by referring to the drugs provided, the clinical condition of the patients, laboratory results, and trustable literature and classified data based on Pharmaceutical Care Network Europe (PCNE) V9.1. The DRPs analyzed included three primary domains for problems and nine primary domains for causes. The three primary domains for problems consist of treatment effectiveness, treatment safety, and others. The nine primary domains for causes consist of drug selection, drug form, dose selection, treatment duration, dispensing, drug use process, patient-related, patient transfer-related, and others. The planned and acceptance domains were not included in this study since the intervention only focused on the T2DM patients. Relative risk, absolute risk reduction and odds ratio were also calculated. The significance of PI on DRP incidence was analyzed using a paired t-test.

Results

Characteristics of the participants

The characteristics of the 106 T2DM outpatients are shown in Table 1. Table 1 shows that the mean age of the T2DM outpatients was 58.61 ± 8.89 (years). Most (54.71%) of them were female. By age range, most of the T2DM outpatients were in the age range of 51–60 (male 19.81% and female 24.52%).

Table 1. Characteristics of the T2DM outpatients (n = 106).

Characteristics	Male (%)	Female (%)
Age of the patients (years):		
18–30	0.94	1.88
31–40	2.83	0.00
41–50	2.83	2.83
51–60	19.81	24.52
61–70	16.98	21.69
>70	1.88	3.77
Total	45.28	54.72
Mean age of the T2DM outpatients	58.61 ± 8.89 (years)	
Comorbidities (%) :		
Hypertension	57.5	
Diabetic neuropathy	35.8	
Congestive heart failure	24.5	
Dyslipidemia	18.9	
Others	34.9	

It was found that the incidence of T2DM increased with age. Three of the most common complications suffered by these T2DM patients were hypertension (57.5%), diabetic neuropathy (35.8%), and congestive heart failure (24.5%). Nearly one-fifth (18.9%) of them had dyslipidemia, and 34.9% of the patients experienced other complications. Other complications experienced by the T2DM outpatients found in this study consisted of chronic kidney disease (CKD), stroke, heart failure (HF), diabetic nephropathy, diabetic ulcers, hypertensive heart disease (HHD), dyspepsia, pneumonia, pulmonary TB, skin and soft tissue infections (SSTI), coronary artery disease (CAD), hyperuricemia, hyperthyroidism, benign prostatic hyperplasia (BPH), chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD) and gout. Drugs provided to the patients to treat T2DM and its complications are shown in Table 2.

Table 2. Treatment provided to the T2DM outpatients (n = 106).

Treatment for T2DM	n	Treatment for T2DM complications	n
Aspart + glargine	33	Gabapentin	60
Metformin + glimepiride	26	Amlodipine	41
Metformin	6	Candesartan	33
Novomix	6	Simvastatin	23
Aspart + levemir	6	B complex	22
Metformin + gliclazide	5	Acetaminophen	10
Apidra + glargine	4	Omeprazole	11
Glimepiride	3	Diclofenac sodium	7
Ryzodeg	3	Ranitidine	6
Metformin + diamicron + pioglitazone	2	Bisoprolol	6
Metformin + glimepiride + pioglitazone	2		
Apidra + levemir	2		
Ryzodeg + metformin	2		
Metformin + glimepiride + acarbose	2		
Gliquidon	1		
Metformin + glikuidon	1		
Novomix + acarbose	1		
Novomix + glimepiride	1		

Drugs provided to the patients to treat T2DM consist of oral antidiabetic and insulin treatment. The most frequently prescribed oral antidiabetics were combinations of metformin and glimepiride (n = 26), the insulin treatment that was most frequently prescribed was a combination of aspart and glargine (n = 33), and the three most frequently prescribed drugs for treating the complications experienced by the T2DM outpatients were gabapentin (n = 60), amlodipine (n = 41) and candesartan (n = 33).

Impact pharmacist-led intervention on DRPs

The incidence of DRPs analyzed on 106 T2DM outpatients at Prof. Dr. Chairuddin P. Lubis Hospital is shown in Table 3. The results of this study showed that 101 (95.28%) and 94 (88.68%) of these patients had DRPs in the CG and PI groups, respectively. The total incidence of DRPs in CG was 263 incidences (2.48 DRPs/patient ± 1.99) and reduced significantly to 205 incidences in the PI group (1.93 DRPs/patient ± 1.47) (p = 0.001). In detail, effectiveness-related DRPs in the CG were 102 incidences (38.78%) and 86 incidences (41.95%) in PI. Safety-related DRPs in the CG consisted of 160 incidences (60.84%) and 118 incidences (57.56) in PI, and other DRPs had one incidence in the CG and PI groups.

Table 3. Incidence of DRPs in the management of T2DM outpatients (n = 106).

Primary Domain	Incidences of DRPs			Paired t-test
	CG	PI	Reduction (%)	
Treatment effectiveness	102	86	15.69	0.001
No effect of drug treatment despite correct use	19	13	31.58	
Effect of drug treatment was not optimal	64	54	15.62	
Untreated symptoms or indication	19	19	0.00	
Treatment safety	160	118	26.25	
Adverse drug events	160	118	26.25	
Others	1	1	0.00	
Unnecessary drug-treatment	1	1	0.00	
Overall DRPs	263	205	22.05	
Mean	2.48 ± 1.99	1.93 ± 1.47	55.00	

Causes of DRPs in the management of T2DM outpatients can be seen in Table 4. The results of this study showed that, of the nine primary domains, two domains that caused DRPs consisted of drug selection (C.1) and patient-related (C.7). Drug selection-related DRPs (C.1) in the CG totaled 180 incidences (68.44%) and 138 incidences (67.58%) in the PI group. The most frequent causes of DRPs were inappropriate combination of drugs (C1.5) with 160 incidences (60.84%) in the CG and 118 incidences (62.5%) in the PI group. Incidences of patient-related DRPs (C.7) in the CG were 83 incidences (31.56%) and 67 incidences

(32.42%) in the PI group. The most frequent cause of DRPs was patients intentionally using/taking less drug than prescribed or not taking the drug at all for whatever reason (C7.1). In the CG there were 72 incidences (27.38%) and in the PI group there were 60 incidences (29.26%).

Table 4. Causes of DRPs in the management of T2DM outpatients (n = 106).

Code	Primary Domain	Incidences of DRPs			Paired t-test
		CG	PI	Reduction (%)	
C	Overall DRPs	263	205	22.05	0.001
C.1	Drug selection	180	138	23.33	
C1.2	No indication for drug	1	1	0.00	
C1.3	Inappropriate combination of drugs	160	118	26.25	
C1.5	No or incomplete drug treatment in spite of existing indication	19	19	0.00	
C.7	Patient related	83	67	19.28	
C7.1	Patient intentionally uses/ takes less drug than prescribed or does not take the drug at all for whatever reason	72	60	16.67	
C7.6	Patient stores drug inappropriately	6	2	66.67	
C7.9	Patient physically unable to use drug/form as directed	5	5	0.00	

Table 5 lists the absolute and relative risk reductions of pharmacist-led intervention for 106 T2DM outpatients. The present study found that the absolute risk reduction of overall DRPs was 6.60%, treatment effectiveness was 15.10%, treatment safety was 3.77%, and others was 0.00%. The relative risk of overall DRPs was 0.931, treatment effectiveness was 0.807, and treatment safety was 0.938.

Table 5. Relative risk, absolute risk reduction and odds ratio with PI compared to CG.

DRPs Domain	Absolute risk (%) in group with		Relative risk	Absolute risk reduction (%)	Odd Ratio
	CG	PI			
	Overall DRPs	95.28			
Treatment effectiveness	78.30	63.20	0.807	15.10	0.476
Treatment safety	61.32	57.55	0.938	3.77	0.855
Others	0.94	0.94	1	0.00	1.000

The odds ratio of overall DRPs with PI compared to CG was 0.388. With regard to treatment effectiveness and treatment safety, ORs were 0.476 and 0.855, respectively. The OR for other domains was 1. Except for the primary domains of other DRPs, all domains have odds ratios and relative risk values less than 1.

Discussion

More than three-quarters of T2DM outpatients in the present study were in the age range above 50 years, with an average age of 58.61 ± 8.89 years. Compared to previous

research, the mean age at diagnosis was 52.91 ± 10.25 years, and the duration of diabetes was 8.06 ± 5.66 years. Depending on their age at diagnosis, the subjects were split into three groups: early-onset DM (≤ 43 years), late-onset DM (44 to 59 years), and elderly-onset DM (≥ 60 years) (Yao et al. 2023). β cell dysfunction led by decreased functional β cell mass puts older people at risk for T2DM (Zhu et al. 2021).

This study showed that the most common antidiabetic regimen provided to outpatients was a combination of glibenclamide and metformin. Metformin was the most commonly administered antidiabetic medication, according to retrospective observational research in a tertiary care hospital (Raphael et al. 2017). Metformin was the most regularly prescribed antidiabetic medication for T2DM patients in a tertiary care hospital, according to another study that examined their patterns of drug usage (Sridhar et al. 2021). In 2022 and 2023, metformin was the most prescribed oral antihyperglycemic drug, accounting for a significant portion of diabetes treatment expenditures (Milićević et al. 2024). The clinical condition of T2DM patients influences the choice of antidiabetic medications.

The present study shows that based on the number of patients, most T2DM patients experience DRPs with various causes. The result of this study is relevant to previous studies about DRPs in the management of T2DM patients. Based on the number of DRPs incidences, similar findings were identified in a retrospective study of 156 patients. Of these patients, 126 (80.8%) had at least one DRPs, for 149 DRPs. The need for additional drug therapy (60/40.3%), non-compliance (51/34.2%), and unnecessary drug therapy (12/8%) were the most common medication-related issues. The reasons why additional drug therapy was required were: 83.3% of the patients needed prophylactic drug therapy (statins and antiplatelets); 11.7% had untreated medical conditions (hypertension, diabetic nephropathy, and diabetic foot ulcers); and 5% needed combination therapy for better efficacy (Belayneh et al. 2021). In another study which included 330 individuals with T2DM, 279 (84.5%) experienced at least 1 DRP, and a total of 455 DRPs were found. The most frequently reported DRPs were untreated symptoms or indications (30.1%) and the effects of drug therapy not optimal (52.7%) (Sheleme et al. 2021). Drug interactions were the most frequent DRPs (36.06% (n = 22)), followed by adverse drug reactions 27.86% (n = 17) and medication non-adherence 24.59% (n = 15), as well as not getting medication 11.47% (n = 7) (Shareef et al. 2021). A similar study in Indonesia shows that 80 of 112 T2DM patients experienced Drug Related Problems (DRPs), resulting in a total of 224 DRPs. The most frequent DRPs were adverse drug effects at 66.52%. Other domains included drugs without indications (15.63%) and drugs not appropriate according to guidelines/formularies (7.14%) (Eka Puspitasari et al. 2023).

The results of this study proved that PI reduced incidences of DRPs, which is confirmed by previous studies concluding that there were consistently fewer DRP incidences in the PI group than in the CG. In a previous study, the PI model significantly increased the number

of patients receiving close monitoring (from 7.7 to 16.9) and the efficacy of pharmacists in solving DRPs (from 13.6 to 20.1 incidences per month)(Li et al. 2020). According to a further investigation, the group receiving CG experienced 128 DRPs, whereas the group receiving PI experienced 39 DRPs. While PI was utilized to manage T2DM, the incidences of DRPs were significantly lower than when standard care was used ($p < 0.001$)(Nasution et al. 2019). A comprehensive analysis of 36 PI trials revealed greater clinical outcomes in the PI groups compared to the standard treatment groups (Pousinho et al. 2016). A systematic analysis examining 59 PI studies related to T2DM patient management revealed significant improvements in patient outcomes compared to standard treatment group (Presley et al. 2019). Previous studies in Asia demonstrated that PI brought significant improvements in glycemic control (Bhurji et al. 2016). The efficacy of PI in reducing the incidence of DRPs was further strengthened by the relative risk value and odds ratio. In general, an odds ratio less than one indicates that the event is less likely to occur in the intervention group compared to the control group. In this study, except for other DRPs domains, all domains had relative risk values and odds ratios of less than 1, indicating that PI reduced the risk and the proportion of DRPs (Choi 2016). This present study implied that PI is important in the management of T2DM patients to reduce the incidence of DRPs.

The results of the present study and previous studies indicated that management of T2DM outpatients accompanied by pharmacist-led intervention is effective in reducing the incidence of DRPs. Reducing the incidence of DRPs can improve clinical outcomes and patient quality of life and minimize T2DM complications and direct medical costs. Beyond dispensing medicines, pharmacists provide patient-oriented instead of product-centered service (Alabkal et al. 2023). Pharmacists are known for their skills in medication reconciliation, drug treatment evaluation, and problem-solving-based care planning. They are also known for their ability to educate patients and their families about illnesses, drugs, and lifestyle modifications (Abdulrhim et al. 2020). Many previous studies have shown that the role of pharmacists in health services for various diseases can increase patients' knowledge and compliance with their medications (Thanmayi et al. 2017; Riwu et al. 2019; Siddiqua et al. 2019; Alissa et al. 2021). A systematic review has shown that 16 policy papers and 10 studies indicate positive evidence from PI was obtained concerning screening individuals at risk, screening uncontrolled patients, managing diabetes, and supporting self-monitoring (Costa et al. 2019). The role of pharmacists in T2DM outpatient management is very important, especially in providing education and counseling to T2DM outpatients, which can improve patient knowledge and compliance with the treatment. The findings of the current study inform health policymakers about the importance of implementing PI in the management of T2DM outpatients by enhancing the role of clinical pharmacists. The enhanced

number of clinical pharmacists and extra courses in hospitals are the acceleration points for implementing PI in Indonesia as well as other developing countries.

Strengths and limitations

Strengths

This quasi-experimental study directly compared and clarified the difference/reduction in DRPs between the CG and the PI group. This study effectively implements clinical pharmacy services for outpatients with T2DM, a population that frequently presents with poor understanding and adherence to their treatment. The quality of these findings is enhanced by the application of PCNE version 9.1, the latest globally recognized standard for DRP analysis. The significant DRP reduction ($p = 0.001$) is strongly supported by odds ratio, absolute risk reduction, and relative risk, with the totality of these analyses indicating a promising effect of the pharmacist intervention in reducing DRPs.

Limitations

The six-month study period, demonstrating short-term benefits, may not be sufficient to evaluate the long-term impact of the PI on reduction of DRPs. The diversity in the clinical characteristics and complication profiles of the outpatients potentially contributes to bias. Further investigation into patient adherence, knowledge, and the cost-effectiveness of pharmacist intervention for T2DM outpatients over the long term would contribute to a more comprehensive study.

Conclusion

Pharmacist-led intervention through patient education and counseling proved to reduce the incidence of DRPs in the management of T2DM outpatients. Health policymakers should consider this finding to improve the management of T2DM outpatients. Sufficient numbers and qualified pharmacists are crucial to educating self-management of T2DM outpatients.

Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

Informed consent from the humans, donors or donors' representatives: The Ethics Committee of Health Research, Universitas Sumatera Utara.

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

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Author contributions

Concept, project administration, investigation, data curation, formal analysis, writing original draft: WW Concept, project administration, supervision, formal analysis, writing original draft:

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text or Supplementary Information.

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Supplementary material 1

The ethical clearance

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Data type: pdf

Explanation note: The ethical clearance of this study was issued by The Ethics Committee of Health Research, Universitas Sumatera Utara No. 341/KEPK/USU/2023.

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